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Physical education in the realization of educational inclusion of students with disabilities as a result of war

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***Abstract.** The article deals with the issue of educational inclusion of students with disabilities as a result of war. The purpose of the work is to identify the potential of physical education in ensuring the educational inclusion of students with disabilities as a result of war in higher education institutions. Research methods: theoretical analysis, systematization, comparison, generalization. Results. It has been found that inclusive physical education is a relatively new direction in the national system of education and science, which studies aspects of physical education of persons with*

disabilities, such as teaching strategies, equipment, environment and assessment and their adaptation to the needs of all students. It has been found that an inclusive educational program is based on the philosophy that every student with a disability due to war with physical or psychological illnesses, without exception, receives quality physical education. It is substantiated that the implementation of educational inclusion of students with disabilities as a result of war requires the substantiation and creation of effective technologies of inclusive physical education, organized based on modern general scientific and special technologies of theory, methodology and practice of physical culture that would provide a high level of physical activity, overcoming health disorders in students with disabilities as a result of war as subjects of the educational process, optimizing the process of adaptation of such students in the environment of the educational institution and achieving As a result of the research work, the current trends in the formation of an inclusive model of physical education for students with war-related disabilities in higher education institutions based on foreign practices in the projection of new domestic educational paradigms were highlighted. Conclusions: Physical education in ensuring educational inclusion for students with war-related disabilities in higher education institutions is implemented based on the principles of tolerance, impartiality and non-discrimination in this process and educational segregation of students with war-related disabilities and limited physical capabilities.

Keywords: *inclusion, education, physical education, adaptation, health disorders.*

Фізичне виховання у реалізації освітньої інклюзії здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни

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***Анотація.** У статті розглянуто питання фізичного виховання здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю. Мета роботи – виявлення потенцій фізичного виховання у забезпеченні освітньої інклюзії для здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни у закладах вищої освіти. Методи дослідження: теоретичний аналіз, систематизація, порівняння, узагальнення. Досліджено, у сучасній вищій школі України інклюзія розглядається як важливий компонент освітнього процесу, що забезпечує можливість для досягнення освітніх і професійних цілей здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни. З'ясовано, що інклюзивне фізичне виховання, орієнтовано на філософію того, що кожен здобувач вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни із фізичними чи психологічними захворюваннями, без винятку отримує якісне фізичне виховання. Обґрунтовано, що реалізація освітньої інклюзії здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни вимагає обґрунтування і створення ефективних*

ПЕДАГОГІЧНА АКАДЕМІЯ: НАУКОВІ ЗАПИСКИ

технологій інклюзивного фізичного виховання, організованого на основі сучасних загальнонаукових і спеціальних технологій теорії, методики і практики фізичної культури які б забезпечували високий рівень фізичної активності, подолання розладів здоров'я у здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни як суб'єктів освітнього процесу, оптимізації адаптації в середовищі навчального закладу та досягненню прогнозованих результатів у ході здобуття ними вищої освіти. У результаті науково-пошукової роботи висвітлено актуальні тенденції формування інклюзивної моделі фізичного виховання для здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни у закладах вищої освіти на основі зарубіжних практик у проєкції нових освітніх парадигм. Висновки. Як міждисциплінарна сукупність практичних і теоретичних знань, інклюзивне фізичне виховання у закладах вищої освіти спрямоване на усунення обмежень здобувачів вищої освіти з інвалідністю внаслідок війни у всіх можливих формах реалізації освітнього процесу, скерованого на їхнє здоров'язбереження задля подолання наявних відхилень у психофізичному стані та усунення фізичних обмежень.

***Ключові слова:** інклюзія, фізична культура, здобувач вищої освіти, освіта, реабілітація, порушення здоров'я.*

Introduction. Since 2014, Ukrainian society has been confronting the russian aggressor. According to the Ukrainian Veteran Fund [1], there are currently 1 million 5 thousand 832 people in Ukraine who have the status of a war invalid, war veteran, or combatant. Of these, about 320 thousand are combatants due to their participation in the ATO. Undoubtedly, the number of such persons will grow as events unfold.

One of the key priorities of Ukraine's current social and educational policy is ensuring that persons with war-related disabilities have the opportunity to receive quality education in accordance with their characteristics, needs, and capabilities.

However, their physical and psychological rehabilitation in the higher education environment is a problem. The main mechanism for implementing this process in higher education institutions is inclusion [2].

It is an inclusion that currently provides an opportunity to obtain quality educational knowledge and a solution to the scientific and practical problem of overcoming health disorders in students [3]. Inclusive physical education is considered [4] an effective tool for realizing the above.

The role and place of physical education in the process of inclusive education given the permanent increase in students with disabilities as a result of the war is now of particular importance, which further actualizes this problem in connection with the ongoing hostilities in Ukraine.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Studies [6, 7] argue that physical education can be an effective tool for educational inclusion for students with disabilities in terms of a positive impact on the quality of life and their functional state. At the same time, the guidelines of the process of improving their health are considered from the standpoint of organizing this process [7], which focuses on taking into account the determinants and model of inclusive education when using forms, means and methods of physical education [8].

Scientists [9-11] are unanimous in the opinion that inclusive physical education in the education system is one of the important structural components of the basis for the implementation of the inclusive process in higher education. It is undoubtedly determined that physical education classes contribute to health promotion, improvement of physical and mental performance, and psychological state.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Along with the need to obtain high-quality professional training in higher education institutions, there is a problem of physical and psychological rehabilitation of students with disabilities as a result of the war. However, the existing scientific literature does

not explore ways to solve the issue of effective and rapid solutions to ensure a high-quality process of educational inclusion based on the use of the inclusive physical education possibilities as the main tool for ensuring the rehabilitation process of students with disabilities as a result of the war.

Meanwhile, we believe that physical education is a simple, accessible, free tool for ensuring educational inclusion for students with disabilities as a result of the war in higher education institutions. The challenges associated with the implementation of educational inclusion that have arisen before the Ukrainian education system have significantly increased since the war.

Given the rapid increase in the number of students with disabilities as a result of the war since the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine and the duration of hostilities, and the virtually complete absence of research and recommendations on the inclusion implementation through physical education tools for students with disabilities as a result of the war in higher education institutions, there is an urgent need to consider the issue of identifying opportunities for physical education in this process.

The purpose of the study is to identify the potential of physical education in ensuring educational inclusion for students with disabilities due to war in higher education institutions.

Objectives of the article:

1. To clarify the understanding of «educational inclusion» for students with disabilities as a result of war in higher education institutions.
2. To identify the potential of PE in the effective implementation of educational inclusion for students with disabilities as a result of war.

Research methods: theoretical analysis, systematization, comparison of different views on the problem under study, generalization of data from scientific, methodological and specialized literature.

Results of the study. Today, the national educational community is facing new challenges: providing a full-fledged opportunity to receive higher education for persons affected by the war, and above all, those who have acquired the status of persons with disabilities as a result of the war. Ukraine has undertaken to harmonize its regulatory framework in accordance with classical human rights normative provisions in accordance with the «Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms» [12], which was ratified in 1997. This process is based on national revival, democracy, humanism, and openness to the assimilation of progressive achievements of world theory and practice.

We cannot agree [13] that today Ukrainian society has an understanding of the need to develop inclusive practices in education. The transformation of social processes from «soviet» to national, depoliticized and de-ideologized is gradual in Ukraine, but it steadily leads to the progressive development of these processes into the current state and promising directions of modernization in accordance with European and world standards.

Today's modernization of the paradigm of national educational inclusion involves the implantation of the basic values of inclusion that have been implemented in many foreign countries for a long time. This, according to [9, 14], involves: eliminating the isolation of any categories of students, using the potential of the existing strong connection between their physical and social, intellectual, spiritual development, and therefore the possibilities of higher education institutions to ensure the full current and future life of students with disabilities as a result of war.

In modern higher education in Ukraine, inclusion is seen as an important component of the educational process [3], which provides an opportunity to achieve the educational and professional goals of students with war-related disabilities. Undoubtedly, each of these students has certain characteristics and limitations that complicate their studies. This requires providing them with quality education in

accordance with their characteristics, needs and capabilities. At the same time, as stated in [15], the most important task is to ensure a high level of health, performance, functional capabilities and physical fitness of students with disabilities.

Since Ukraine has virtually no experience of inclusive practices for students with war-related disabilities in higher education institutions, we believe that the development of their physical education should be a priority in the educational policy of higher education. An inclusive program based on the philosophy that every student with a war-related disability with physical or psychological illnesses, without exception, receives quality physical education.

Therefore, efforts should be directed at substantiating and creating effective technologies of physical education, organized based on modern general scientific and special technologies of theory, methodology and practice of physical culture that would ensure a high level of physical activity, overcoming health disorders in students with disabilities as a result of war as subjects of the educational process, optimizing adaptation in the environment of the educational institution and achieving the predicted results in the course of their higher education.

Inclusive physical education is a relatively new area in the national system of education and science that studies aspects of physical education of persons with disabilities and related disabilities. According to [4], the main goal of inclusive physical education is to form and develop motor activity, physical and psychological abilities that ensure the adaptation of persons with disabilities to their health status, environment, society and various activities.

Our proposals are based on the inextricable interconnection of the learning process and physical education. The best international experience shows that physical education is not the prerogative of only healthy students, and that students even with such severe disabilities as blindness, spinal cord injury, cerebral palsy, etc. can be active participants in physical education.

In the EU and developed countries, inclusive physical education is seen as a tool to provide people with war-related disabilities with a social “way out,” improve their physical skills and eliminate existing health conditions. We have attempted to highlight the content and objectives of inclusive physical education in higher education institutions for students with disabilities in developed countries, which is implemented following several dimensions:

- social: availability of physical education resources in higher education institutions that ensure the implementation of inclusion;
- personal: personal development, mastering new knowledge, formation and development of physical education skills and abilities;
- cognitive: forming an understanding of the specifics of the physical education process, searching for and using various ways and means of physical education in practice, setting goals and making adjustments to the process of inclusive physical education.

In general, a distinctive feature of inclusive physical education in foreign countries is its dynamism, as there is a constant adaptation of learning conditions to the individual characteristics of each student. Therefore, the Ukrainian practice of educational inclusion primarily requires the training of inclusive physical education specialists who fully possess inclusive competence, which now belongs to the new areas of professional training. At the same time, the world and the EU have accumulated considerable experience in this field of knowledge, which can be useful in solving the problem of forming highly qualified pedagogical staff of a new generation, capable of acting at the level of the requirements of international professional standards, who should be prepared in advance specifically for working with persons with disabilities as a result of war and applying modern and effective pedagogical technologies of physical education.

As it has been found, inclusive physical education for students with disabilities is a common practice in the European and global education systems. An urgent issue of the national education system is to update the content of methods in the field of inclusive physical education and to prepare teachers for future teaching activities in the context of inclusive education at all levels of education and upbringing. At the same time, the leading task is to promote health and a healthy lifestyle based on general physical education practices. We believe that advocacy work is needed to generate information about inclusive physical education as a crucial opportunity to ensure the quality educational inclusion of students with disabilities as a result of war in the educational environment of higher education.

It is extremely important to develop motivation for physical education classes for students with war-related disabilities in higher education institutions. Unlike the EU and leading countries of the world, Ukraine does not have institutions for involving such students in systematic physical education classes as a means of their educational inclusion.

Instead, the implementation of inclusion in physical education requires the acquisition of skills in effective communication with higher education students with war-related disabilities, the study of motivational techniques, targeted educational and informational work, and the coverage of international and domestic experience and achievements to develop the need for physical self-improvement in students with war-related disabilities and, consequently, physical education classes.

In this sense, it is important to intensify and coordinate the actions of the educational community, initiate and implement projects, including in partnership with foreign higher education institutions, aimed at ensuring an appropriate level of inclusive physical education as a means of educational inclusion of students with war-related disabilities.

The implementation of empirical research in the field of inclusive physical education and the implementation of research results in practice, the combination of theoretical and practical, their focus on achieving certain standards of inclusive physical education for students with disabilities due to war is at a very high level in foreign countries, and is confirmed by scientific publications.

We are impressed by the opinion [4] that the possibilities of physical education in ensuring educational inclusion for students with war-related disabilities in higher education institutions ensure the elimination of social segregation in attracting them to participate in physical education on an equal footing with all participants in the educational process. Thus, the philosophy of inclusion is being formed in this process.

Science, experience and practice of the advanced EU countries and the world confirm that the development of new and improved physical education technologies constantly creates new programs (applications) to help higher education students with war-related disabilities in various ways, providing the latest physical education techniques to improve physical development and eliminate health defects. Among the structural innovations is the creation of centers for physical education and sports for students with disabilities in higher education institutions, modeled after those in Western Europe.

It should be noted that full physical activity is often the first thing that higher education students with disabilities are deprived of as a result of war and injuries. At first, they face restrictions everywhere. Later, they have problems with self-esteem and self-realization. As a result, higher education students with disabilities find themselves on the sidelines, often on their initiative. As a result, the physical trauma of war becomes a factor in psychological problems. This is also the subject of research on inclusive physical education, and inclusive physical education, respectively, as a means of eliminating such problems.

It has been proven [9] that lack of movement during the day and constant sitting cause anxiety and depression, while physical activity, on the contrary, provides positive emotions. An effective mechanism for preserving and strengthening the psychological state of students with disabilities is the creation of appropriate pedagogical conditions for the implementation of their physical education in the course of study to disseminate the best inclusive educational practices. The latter is due to the need to ensure the full realization of their physical development during the educational process as a factor in regulating their psychological state.

Therefore, the organization of inclusive physical education is due to the importance and necessity of taking measures to create the most favorable conditions for improving the psychological state of students with disabilities as a result of the war. This is ensured by leveling the impact of natural experiences under martial law to counteract the challenges that inevitably occur in a war situation [2].

Thus, to summarize, we consider physical education in ensuring educational inclusion for students with disabilities as a result of war in higher education institutions as a rehabilitation and corrective process, the foundations of which are related to those defined by inclusive education. The content of the proposed model, its basis is the forms, means and methods of physical education, primarily those that use inclusive physical education. This necessitates further research in this direction, in particular by developing (modernizing) innovative practices of pedagogical content, physical therapy and technologies of inclusive physical education.

Conclusions. At the moment, in Ukraine, given the permanent increase in students with disabilities as a result of the war in society due to prolonged hostilities, special attention is paid to the possibilities of educational inclusion to provide such students with a full-fledged education, individualized, accessible, based on needs and capabilities, aimed at maximizing their self-realization during the term of study. This approach is a creative combination of key components of correctional development and

interaction of participants in the educational process (teachers and students with war-related disabilities) in the course of inclusive physical education aimed at overcoming the impact of the consequences of war to eliminate disorders in their physical and mental health.

In the context of European integration, approaching the European space, based on national traditions and achievements, it is planned to build a national strategy for the development of inclusive physical education in the context of general approaches of the world educational community, which are determined by global transformations in this area.

Therefore, we consider the possibilities of physical education in ensuring educational inclusion for students with war-related disabilities in higher education institutions based on the principles of tolerance, impartiality and non-discrimination in the process of their physical education, rejection of educational segregation of students with war-related disabilities and limited physical capabilities.

Prospects for further research include building a model of inclusive physical education for students with war-related disabilities.

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